

ANALYZING TERMS OF “FRAME” AND “SCENARIO” IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Annotation

This article examines the emergence of the field of cognitive linguistics, the expression and application of the concepts of frame, scenario and concept, which are important elements of this field, in English and Uzbek. The research and conclusions of many linguists working in this field are analyzed.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, concept, frame, scenario, concept, term, fear, cognitive layer.

The first theories about the emergence of the concept of “Cognitive Linguistics”, one of the important terms in the field of linguistics, are mainly evident in the scientific works of American linguists J. Miller, J. Bruner, J. Lakoff, R. Langaker, R. Jackendoff. The word “Cognitive” is derived from the English word “cognize”. It expresses meanings such as to know, to understand, to comprehend.

If we look at the etymology of the term cognitive linguistics, this field began to emerge in linguistics in the 1970s, during which many researchers became increasingly interested in the relationship between language and consciousness, but they did not conduct sufficient research on the specific features and functions of language. Later, linguists Wallace Chafe, Charles Fillmore, George Lakoff, Ronald Langaker, and Leonard Talme conducted their research in this field. These linguists began to develop ideas based on linguistic theory that describe language, which approached a certain set of phenomena and concepts. An important aspect of the ideas researched by the above linguists is that the most essential central concept for language is its meaning. They put forward the theory that linguistic structures should be based on the function of expressing meanings, and therefore the relationship between meaning and form is an important object of linguistic analysis.

By 1980, linguists Lakoff and Langaker began to study linguistic problems from a cognitive perspective in their research. It is worth noting that cognitive linguistics studies all the basic concepts of language as a cognitive mechanism, that is, an information processing system. According to the linguist Sh. Safarov, “The task of cognitive linguistics is to acquire and store knowledge using language, to apply and

transmit language in practice, and in general, to conduct a deep scientific study of the system and structure of language as a reflection of thought in the human brain.” Also, the basis of the concept is united by three things: concept, image, and linguistic meaning. First of all, the formation of a concept is associated with imagination, and the end point of this process is the materialization of the concept as a sign of language. This means that this concept that has arisen in our thinking has a certain material name.

The main goal of cognitive linguistics at the current stage of its formation as a science is to describe and model the structures of concepts as the main elements of cognitive science.

If we talk about the origin of the word “concept”, which is one of the important elements of the field of cognitive linguistics, this word is derived from the Latin word “conceptus”, which means “idea, concept”. The term “concept” has been actively used in linguistic literature since the early 90s.

One of the next major branches of cognitive linguistics is the cognitive script, a term first explored in 1977 by Roger Shank and Robert Abelson in their book "Scenarios, Plans, Goals, and Understanding: A Study of the Structures of Human Knowledge." The smaller parts of a script, such as roles and main goals, are called slots. A slot represents a chain of different causes that represent knowledge about events. Each frame consists of several slots. The term "slot" was introduced into linguistics by researchers in artificial intelligence, just like the term frame.

In modern linguistics, the term frame is defined as follows:

- a frame is a concept that has been formed around a concept and contains information about what is important, customary, and possible for that concept within a given culture;
- the cognitive structure existing in the phenomenological sphere of the individual is based on assumptions and knowledge about typical situations, the qualities and relationships of real and hypothetical objects;
- a type of cognitive model that represents knowledge and thoughts related to specific, frequently recurring situations, a body of knowledge that unites many areas associated with a particular linguistic form.

Therefore, the concept of a frame can represent information that is relevant for a particular culture. Also, linguist S.A. Jabotinskaya distinguished five types of frames according to their structure:

- a subject-centered frame (frame) is understood as a system of sentences with several predicates attached to a logical object, which characterize the object with quantitative, qualitative, location, time, and value parameters.

- a frame (frame), the components of which are united by common relations or subjects, is called taxonomic.

- in a frame of action, several objects interacting in a certain space and time are assigned semantic roles that reflect the active nature of the relationship between them: agent, patient, instrument, addressee, beneficiary, cause, result, etc.

- frames expressing ownership express the connection between objects, which is realized through the ownership relationship, presented in the form of the predicate "ownership". This frame has three types: 1) owner - property, 2) container - filling, 3) whole - part.

-The basic associative frame shows the similarity relationships between objective entities based on the convergence of concepts in human thinking.

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